

LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT APPROACH IN BIOINSOUTH PROJECT

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THE CONTEXT

Bio-based economy in Southern Europe faces several challenges that emphasize the necessity of development of bio-based activities with reduced environmental footprint. Life cycle assessment is recognized as the most appropriate approach for addressing the environmental aspects of bioprocesses. However, lack of primary data and difficulties on the interpretation of results hamper the adoption of this methodology at industrial level.

OUR OBJECTIVES

- ✓ Review of existing LCA of bioeconomy processes
- ✓ Development of LCA studies of the most relevant bioprocesses in the context of BioINSouth
- ✓ Identify hotspot and provide recommendations to improve the environmental performance of bio-based industries
- ✓ Integration of LCA into the BioINSouth toolkit

THE METHODOLOGY

1) Assessment of 10 bioprocesses: Cradle-to-gate LCAs with inventory data from scientific literature (see table). Attributional approach. Following PEF recommendations. Using Simapro 9.6 and Ecoinvent 3.10 as database :

Sector	Feedstock	Outputs	Reference	Year
Agricultural biomass	Almond shells	Oligosaccharides, lignin, cellulose nanocrystals	Sillero et al.	2021
	Pomegranate peels	Ellagic acid, lignin, pectin	Shinde et al.	2020
	Citrus peel waste	Ethanol, limonene, methanol	Joglekar et al.	2019
	Rice straw	Ethanol, food grade CO ₂ , methanol, silica, inorganics	Parajuli et al.	2019
	Grape marc	Vermicompost, Polyphenols-rich extract, seed oil, brandy	Cortés et al.	2020
Industrial waste	Wheat straw	Ethanol	Sreekumar et al.	2017
	Barley straw & brewers spent grains	Xylooligosaccharides, ethanol	González-García et al.	2018
Forest biomass	Poplar biomass	Acetic acid, lignin	Budberg et al.	2020
	Alfalfa biomass	Lactic acid, feed protein, fodder silage	Parajuli et al.	2017
Aquaculture biomass	Microalgae biomass	Polysaccharides	Saadia et al.	2017

2) Clustering with KEY projects* gathering feedback/ recommendations related to:

- Functional unit definition
- System boundaries definition
- Impact categories
- Modelling approaches
- Allocation method
- Most common hotspots

* BIORECER BIOTRANSFORM C4B CALIMERO ESCIB LCA4BIO SUSTRACK

3) HUBs: BioINSouth aims to establish regional HUBs in eight European regions (Campania – Italy, Andalusia and Asturias – Spain, Centro – Portugal, Nouvelle-Aquitaine – France, Peloponnese – Greece, Cyprus and Slovenia)

The project started mapping the various life cycle assessment (LCA) approaches for environmental studies of bioeconomy. The application of the PEF framework to ten bioprocesses identified in the literature was complemented by considering the feedback received on the methodological recommendations from the EU consulted projects. Building on the LCA work in BioINSouth, project Hubs will use studies and LCA data (which will be made available via the future project toolkit) to inform their decision-making processes and ensure the sustainable development of the bioeconomy in southern European regions.

RESULTS

Figure 1: Grape marc valorisation (Weighted impacts)

From the LCA studies of the 10 bioprocesses, the most relevant environmental impact categories are climate change (CC), eutrophication (freshwater) (FEU), resource use (fossil) (RFD), water use (WU) and particulate matter (PM) (see figure 1, example of results obtained for the grape marc valorisation process).

From the clustering process with other EU projects, the feedback received evidences that there is no harmonisation on LCA applied to bioeconomy, as different approaches to model impacts are suggested. However, in terms of indicators, climate change is highlighted that the most relevant aspect that should be considered in all LCA studies. Figure 2 shows that opinions are divided regarding modelling choices- allocation or consequential (1 out of 7 respondents said that it depends).

Figure 2: Allocation or consequential

Based on the priorities of the HUBs, it is envisaged that LCA data, that will be integrated into the BioINSouth toolkit, will guide the decision-making process in relation to agricultural feedstocks, industrial bio-waste and forest biomass.

